

USING VIDEO MATERIALS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the effective methods of "formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students using authentic video materials in foreign language teaching". Learning a foreign language can be difficult for any language learner. In the process of language learning, the selection of audio and video materials presented by the teacher to language learners of different ages is carried out step by step. Video materials play an important role in this process.

KEY WORDS: Authentic video materials, communicative competence, foreign language, method, teaching method.

In recent years, learning a foreign language and being able to speak it independently has become a basic requirement in various areas of society. In particular, if we look at the global scale, their main requirements for new personnel are to be able to communicate in a foreign language and to be aware of computer technologies. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1875 on the "National Program of Personnel Training" and "Measures to Further Improve the System of Learning Foreign Languages" adopted by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan ``learning shows that the state is a matter of importance. At this point, we should consider teaching a foreign language based on authentic video materials as a solution to the fulfillment of the above requirements and easing the tasks of preparing the learner

for real life situations as the main tool of language education based on communication.

In addition, authentic video materials help in language teaching as an alternative view of the real life situation. The popularization of authentic audio-video materials lies in their ability to create an interactive language environment for language learners, says Russian scientist G.A. Vorobyov. It has also been determined in science that the main part of the data is made up of moving speeches in video materials. The study and research on the application of this method to the lesson led to the following conclusions. - The use of authentic video materials, first of all, provides the language learner with all the features of the spoken language of certain social groups in a specific situation (emotional coloring, clarity for understanding, and its clear reach to the learner) in one or another foreign language) provides realistic communication. - authentic video materials help to dramatically improve speaking and listening skills, which are of primary importance for language learners. The second unique aspect of using authentic video materials in the lesson is the difficulty of the studied language, the variety of words, the speed of speech, the richness of various lexical units. This helps the language learner to clearly and fluently learn a language that is not his mother tongue. Because the use of puns, sarcasms, lexical units known only to native speakers in the videos presented based on real reality has a very good effect.

There are three traditional stages (PREWATCHING, WHILE-WATCHING AND POST-WATCHING stages) of using audio-video materials in the lesson: - the pre-show stage; (the stage before using the authentic video material) - the demonstration stage (the stage when the video material is shown) - the stage after the demonstration (the stage of using authentic video material). In order to conduct effective training based on the above-mentioned method and to achieve the intended result, the pedagogue is required to organize the lesson

based on the typology of exercises in accordance with the task of each stage. The first stage is aimed at preparing language learners for the video demonstration, and includes important tasks such as motivating students, getting them interested in the lesson, familiarizing them with the topic, and activating existing knowledge.

We now have more access than ever to video. News programs, adverts, comedies, documentaries, dramas, academic lectures are available in digital format via the internet. Most of these resources weren't originally created as teaching materials. So it serves a real-world communicative purpose. Some materials are authentic resources adapted for language teaching. Authentic material not originally produced for ELT purposes, but adapted to different grades [2]. There are some positive characteristics of using video in the process of learning foreign languages: the class does not require dimming, and therefore, the contact of teacher with learners is continuous; video provides the possibility of using different modes of operation, e.g. freeze frame, using only video track (with audio track turned off) etc.; videos can easily be used for different types of work: individual, pair, group, collective [3]; video equipment allows to split movie into desired number of clips, depending on the objectives of individual needs and characteristics of learners to continue working with each clip separately. When teaching the perception of speech by ear, it is necessary, first of all, to develop aural skills and speech hearing with the support of native speakers. And in this case, it is the authentic audio video texts that allow the students to hear the speech of the native speakers, which reflects the living reality, the peculiarities of the national culture. Most importantly, the authentic material provokes the students' cognitive interest, the willingness to discuss problems, and, therefore, contributes to their motivation to learn a foreign language. If the learner perceives foreign speech, then he begins to realize that all his efforts spent on learning a foreign language were not in vain. Thus, the main task of the teacher at the stage of work

with authentic material is the selection of audio or video material that would be interesting, informative, accessible to understanding, corresponded to the modern reality of a foreign language society and would create favorable conditions for mastering new regional information, behavior of native speakers, would facilitate their familiarity with the people's way of life, its culture [5].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the authentic video material adapted to the audience of language learners on the subject allows the students to see and listen to the necessary information and understand through gestures, to fully understand the cultural characteristics of the presented film. at the same time, a set of goal-oriented exercises based on them serves to increase the communicative competence of the language learner.

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